

Mitigating The Impact of Conflict on Humanitarian Aid in Sudan: Strategies for Sustainable Solutions

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Executive Summary

This paper analyzes the challenges and strategies for ensuring effective humanitarian aid delivery in Sudan amidst ongoing conflict. It explores the impact of the conflict on aid distribution, highlighting issues such as resource scarcity, logistical barriers, and health crises. It incorporates qualitative data from interviews and surveys, offering recommendations to improve aid resilience through localized capacity building, feedback mechanisms, and innovative approaches. The paper provides actionable insights for policymakers and humanitarian actors seeking sustainable solutions in conflict zones.

On 15th April, Sudan plunged into a conflict of alarming scale that has expanded to many states. Which has significantly affected humanitarian aid delivery (OCHA,2023). Consequently, an estimated 6.3 million individuals have been internally displaced¹(IMO,2024).

The conflict distressed the health system, with around 60 attacks on facilities, leaving 70% of hospitals non-operational and millions without essential care, increasing morbidity and mortality (Rawa,2024; Alaa et al.,2023; Albarodi,2023).

Sudan's humanitarian needs are vast and multifaceted, as millions require urgent assistance, including food, water, shelter, and healthcare (IMO,2024).

The conflict has strained host communities' resources, leading to overcrowded health facilities and shortages of medical supplies and personnel, exacerbating health crises for both displaced and host populations, highlighting the need for international intervention (UNHCR,2023; Khogali,2023; Albarodi,2023).

Eventually, the conflict has left around 25 million people in need of humanitarian aid (IMMAP,2024). aid in conflict-affected regions – like Sudan – faces significant challenges.

This study assesses the impacts of conflict on aid effectiveness, explores evolving community needs, and examines innovative approaches to ensure aid continuity, offering actionable recommendations to enhance aid resilience in Sudan.

Research Questions and Objectives: aims to provide valuable insights into aid effectiveness by answering these questions:

1. How has the conflict affected aid delivery, and what challenges do humanitarian organizations face?
2. How have the needs of affected communities evolved, and how have aid responses adapted?
3. What innovative approaches have ensured aid continuity?

Research objectives focus on addressing these questions.

Significance Of the Study: lies in its multifaceted contributions to addressing conflict and aid delivery challenges in Sudan, informing tailored response strategies and enhancing aid

¹ As of February 2024.

effectiveness. ultimately providing insights and actionable strategies to improve aid resilience.

Research Methodology

Research Design: This study uses qualitative research to explore conflict's impact on humanitarian aid, aiming for in-depth insights into stakeholders' experiences.

Data Collection: utilizes two primary methods: semi-structured interviews and survey conducted through one-on-one short interviews.

Semi-Structured Interviews: were conducted with three members of aid agencies from 15–20 May, 2024, to gain detailed insights into the challenges and adaptations in aid delivery during the conflict. Two interviewees, current employees of international aid agencies who requested anonymity to protect their employment, had their agency names and job titles kept confidential. The third interviewee, is a former volunteer in an international aid agency.

Surveys through One-on-One Short Interviews: To understand the evolution of affected communities' needs throughout different stages of the conflict and how aid responses adapted, a survey was conducted from 16–19 May. This method was chosen for several reasons:

1. Reduction of data cleaning, as responses are clarified and recorded accurately in real time.
2. Ensuring participants understand questions and provide relevant answers, minimizing misinterpretation.
3. Clarifying that no aid would be provided for participation, maintaining research integrity.
4. Participant preference for speaking rather than filling out forms, increasing participation.
5. Practicality and effectiveness given technical and educational barriers.
6. Deeper insights and comprehensive understanding through verbal interactions.
7. Providing humanitarian actors with first-hand feedback from displaced persons.

Collected answers – sample of 90 participants – were entered into Google Forms by the researcher on 18–19 May.

Data Analysis Data analysis was conducted from 20-21 May, using Google Sheets. The researcher conducted all stages of data collection, cleaning, and analysis, ensuring consistency and a deep understanding of data.

Overall, this methodology combines interviews and survey to gather qualitative data, aiming to provide a thorough understanding of the impact of conflict on humanitarian aid delivery.

Study Limitations:

1. **Data Constraints:** Security concerns limited data access, affecting representativeness and generalizability.
2. **Contextual Specificity:** Findings may be unique to Sudan and not applicable to other conflict-affected areas.
3. **Temporal Constraints:** Focus on the period since April 15th restricts depth of analysis and may render findings less relevant over time.
4. **Regional Focus:** Concentration on Northern State may not represent other regions, especially western states with protracted conflicts.

Despite these limitations, the study aims to provide valuable insights into the impact of conflict on humanitarian aid and offer evidence-based recommendations.

Literature Review: synthesizes findings from four key studies to explore strategies for mitigating the impact of conflict on aid delivery and fostering sustainable solutions:

A. Impact of Conflict on Aid Delivery

Assal in his paper “Is it the Fault of NGOs Alone? Aid and Dependency in Eastern Sudan” highlights the multifaceted challenges that NGOs face in conflict zones, such as political instability, security issues, and logistical constraints. These systemic problems exacerbate the difficulties in delivering aid effectively. NGOs are often unfairly blamed for these shortcomings, while the broader context of conflict plays a crucial role in hampering their efforts (CMI,2020).

This perspective aligns with the findings of Rose in her paper “Cultivating Resilience in Chaos: Localization as a Mechanism for Sustainability and Inner Development in Syria’s Humanitarian Crisis” which emphasizes the importance of localizing aid to improve its cultural relevance and sustainability. Local actors, due to their closeness and understanding

of affected communities, can often navigate these challenges more effectively, although they require adequate support and resources from international partners (MDPI,2022).

B. Evolving Needs and Adaptation of Aid Responses

Rose in her paper “The Provision of Humanitarian Aid in Complex Emergencies: A Case Study of Somalia” provides insights into how civil society organizations (CSOs) have adapted their strategies to continue delivering aid amidst conflict. By leveraging local networks and knowledge, CSOs have been able to implement innovative approaches that ensure the continuity of aid delivery. These adaptations are crucial for meeting the evolving needs and priorities of affected communities, which change as the conflict progresses (CORE,2010).

The paper “A Framework for Effective Collaboration with Crisis-Affected Communities” further elaborates on the importance of involving crisis-affected communities in the decision-making process. By adopting participatory approaches, humanitarian organizations can better align their efforts with the actual needs of these communities, leading to more effective and sustainable aid outcomes (MDPI,2022).

C. Innovative Approaches for Ensuring Aid Continuity

The literature emphasizes several innovative approaches that have proven successful in conflict settings. Localization is a key strategy; by empowering local actors and building their capacity, humanitarian efforts can become more resilient and responsive to the dynamic challenges of conflict (MDPI,2022).

The role of CSOs in implementing grassroots initiatives that utilize local knowledge and resources, thereby ensuring aid continuity despite the conflict. These initiatives demonstrate the potential of localized approaches to overcome the barriers posed by conflict and deliver effective aid (CORE,2010).

The literature highlights the complex nature of delivering aid in conflict zones like Sudan, advocating for a multifaceted approach involving systemic problem-solving, empowering local stakeholders, and engaging affected communities in decision-making.

- **Challenges Faced by Humanitarian Actors in conflict-affected areas**

humanitarian actors in Sudan have faced numerous challenges that significantly impede their operations, as:

- 1. Security threats and Access Constraints:**

The security situation in Sudan remains highly volatile, with frequent clashes and attacks on humanitarian personnel² and infrastructure. Such insecurity has led to the evacuation of international staff, inducing a shortage of aid workers, and restricting access to critical areas³, eventually hindering the overall aid outcomes as stated by Moslehi et al., 2015.

The deteriorating security environment has intensified the difficulty in reaching affected populations⁴, further complicating the humanitarian response (IMMAP,2024).

“Aid agencies have been targeted by local criminal gangs, the RSF, SAF, and militia units seeking monetary gain and access to vehicles and buildings. Such groups have looted aid agency supplies and equipment on a large scale. On 21 August, the World Food Program (WFP) reported that in addition to one of its logistics hubs in south-central Sudan having been overrun, over 40,000 tons of its food assistance in Sudan had been stolen since mid-April. It is possible that some of the looted items from aid agencies have been sold at so-called “Dagalo markets” that the RSF has established across Khartoum, Darfur, and Kordofan regions to sell looted goods” (Insecurity Insight,2023).

Consequently, aid provision within conflict zones was rather completely halted or faced massive disruptions. For instance, Médecins Sans Frontières was forced to suspend work and withdraw staff from Madani Teaching Hospital, “which is the only functional hospital for hundreds of thousands of people in Al Jazirah state” (MSF,2024).

- 2. Bureaucratic and Logistical Barriers:**

Humanitarian operations in Sudan are significantly hindered by bureaucratic obstacles. According to ACAPS (2024), obtaining necessary visas, permits and clearances for movement of international aid workers and goods importing remains a protracted process, delaying the delivery of essential services.

² According to reports, humanitarian actors have faced many security threats in many states over the past year, the latest recorded incident was the abduction of 17 aid volunteers in Khartoum state in May 2024. See report [here](#)

³ Sudan war: RSF rejects proposed humanitarian aid route to Darfur. Africanews, 25 March 2024. Available [here](#) (Accessed: 2 May 2024).

⁴ Sudan’s Humanitarian Coordinator calls for an immediate ceasefire in Al Fasher to safeguard civilians. UNOCHA, 15 May 2023. Available [here](#) (Accessed: 17 May 2024).

Logistical challenges are exacerbated by damaged infrastructure, including roads and bridges, which disrupt supply chains and make it difficult to reach remote communities (World Vision,2023).

3. Resource Scarcity:

The conflict has caused a severe scarcity of resources, affecting both financial and material support. World Vision Annual Report (2023) emphasizes that funding shortfalls have severely undermined the capacity of humanitarian actors to respond to increasing needs. Additionally, local resources such as food, medical supplies, and fuel are in short supply, leading to inflated costs and obstructing relief efforts (Sudan Famine Prevention Plan,2024).

4. Coordination and Communication Challenges:

Effective coordination among humanitarian actors is critical but often hampered by the chaotic environment in Sudan's conflict-affected areas.

Fragmentation among armed groups and a lack of a unified command structure complicate negotiations for safe passage and coordinated response efforts (ACAPS,2024).

Communication breakdowns within and between organizations further impede information sharing and collaborative efforts, leading to inefficiencies and gaps in aid delivery (IMMAP,2024).

5. Health and Sanitation Crisis:

The conflict has led to a public health crisis, characterized by the collapse of healthcare infrastructure and a surge in communicable diseases. Access to clean water and sanitation facilities has deteriorated, heightening the risk of outbreaks such as cholera (Sudan Scenarios,2023).

The compromised health system has left millions without adequate medical care, necessitating urgent interventions to prevent a humanitarian catastrophe (World Vision,2023).

6. Economic and Social Disruption:

The conflict has caused economic disruption, exacerbating poverty and food insecurity, with inflation making basic necessities unaffordable (Sudan Famine Prevention Plan,2024). Moreover, social services, including education and welfare programs, have suffered, deepening the crisis (IMMAP,2024).

In conclusion, humanitarian actors in Sudan face complex challenges including security issues, bureaucratic impediments, logistical constraints, resource scarcity, coordination difficulties, health crises, and economic disruptions. These issues – hindering effective responses – are common in conflict zones as noted by Moslehi et al. Addressing them requires immediate international support and long-term resilience strategies for sustainable recovery.

- **Case Study: Northern State**

The conflict has significantly strained Northern State, with over 362,000⁵ internally displaced persons (IDPs) mostly from Khartoum, constituting 10% of all IDPs nationwide (ACAPS,2023). Displacement has heightened vulnerabilities and increased the need for humanitarian aid.

As of February 2024, Northern State hosts one national NGO, one international NGO, three government entities, two UN agencies, and one Red Cross organization, providing aid in nutrition, protection, shelter, non-food items, and WASH (ACAPS,2023).

The limited aid presence is due to logistical challenges and regional prioritization. Despite the stable security situation, the Northern State's need for humanitarian intervention is less perceived (ACAPS,2023).

Similar Characteristics: Northern, Red Sea, River Nile, and Kassala States share geographical proximity, economic activities focused on agriculture and trade, and similar infrastructure levels, facilitating some generalizability of findings across these regions.

- **Challenges Specific to Northern State**

Data analysis of interviews and survey⁶ highlighted the following main challenges facing humanitarian actors:

1. **Increased Demand and Resources Strain:**

The IDPs influx has strained local resources, prompting organizations like the Sudanese Red Crescent to expand their operations. Moreover, economic and social disruptions caused by conflict have exacerbated the situation, leaving many IDPs unable to afford basic necessities, thus increasing the urgency for shelter and food, according to the Famine Prevention Plan

⁵ As of 25 August 2023.

⁶ To check the interviews' data, see [here](#) . and [here](#) for survey data.

(2024), significant economic losses are prevalent among IDPs, particularly those experiencing multiple displacements.

Survey's data illustrate that, upon displacement, 42.70% of the displaced once considered shelter a high priority, which increased to 53.93% after 6-12 months. Conversely, the low priority for shelter decreased from 52.81% to 43.82%, highlighting a persistent and growing need for stable housing.

For those displaced twice, the initial high priority for shelter was 42.22%, which surged to 54.44% after 6-12 months, while low priority decreased from 53.33% to 43.33%. This trend emphasizes the severe economic losses from multiple displacements and heightened need for shelter.

Moreover, initially, only 8.99% of displaced once prioritized food supplies as a high priority, which surged significantly to 22.47% after 6-12 months, indicating growing food insecurity.

Similarly, for those displaced twice, high priority for food increased from 8.89% to 23.33%. The low priority for food supplies decreased from 84.27% to 56.18% for those displaced once and from 84.44% to 55.56% for those displaced twice, reflecting an increasing urgency for food. (see the graph below)

Moreover, a notable proportion of respondents (70%) received aid twice, while 12% received aid three times, and 18% received aid only once. Notably, there was an approximate gap of at least 3 to 4 months between each instance of aid receipt.

Overall, displacement disrupts economic stability, making shelter and food critical needs. Repeated displacements increase aid reliance, highlighting long-term economic and social impacts.

Effective aid must combine immediate relief with sustained support to address both short-term and long-term needs, enhancing resilience and recovery.

2. Health Crisis:

Interview data indicated a surge in healthcare needs during the first three months of displacement, prompting aid agencies to train volunteers from both host and displaced communities in first aid and nursing to mitigate caregivers' shortages.

Contrary, survey data showed that only 7.78% of respondents initially prioritized health supplies as a high priority, which decreased slightly to 6.67% after 6-12 months.

The inconsistency between the interview and survey data can be explained in two ways; Firstly, aid workers likely anticipated and responded rapidly to the increased demand, as suggested by the interviews. Secondly, the survey data may have missed capturing the initial surge in healthcare needs, as it focused on static periods; immediately upon arrival and then 6-12 months into displacement. This highlights the dynamic nature of IDPs needs and the limitations of static data in reflecting these dynamics.

3. Localization and Mismanagement Challenges:

Interviews revealed significant challenges in localization and collaboration, contrasting with Jo Rose's (2024) findings which celebrate localization as a success factor in humanitarian aid.

Issues of mismanagement and corruption surfaced, serving personal interests and hindering aid effectiveness. Some aid actors suggest minimizing collaboration with local entities to avoid these pitfalls, indicating a need for further research to develop context-specific solutions for Sudan.

Furthermore, trust and hostility issues have emerged, interviews showed that IDPs feel neglected and cheated, leading to verbal hostility and resistance to queue management. Conversely, survey data showed a strong call for respectful treatment of displaced individuals. As, suggestions from IDPs for improving support indicated a strong preference for more respectful treatment, with 15.56% of respondents emphasizing the need for aid to

be provided in a dignified manner. This was the most prevalent suggestion, surpassing other important recommendations such as providing aid regularly (7.78%), reducing aid queues (5.56%), and offering job opportunities (3.33%). The emphasis on respectful aid provision highlights the importance of dignity and respect in humanitarian work, suggesting that how aid is delivered can be as crucial as aid itself.

Queue management issues exacerbate these problems, as many aid agencies distribute aid from offices in Marawi city, requiring IDPs to travel long distances.

Meanwhile, survey data indicates that 60% of IDPs are in villages, 20% in a city, and 20% in a town. This travel incurs transportation costs that many IDPs cannot afford, and aid queues are often long, mismanaged, and exposed to the sun, leading to prolonged waits and disputes with office staff.

Additionally, logistical and transport issues, including poor road infrastructure and high transportation costs – paid by IDPs in order to receive aid – further hinder timely and efficient aid delivery, eventually, corruption and mismanagement among volunteers and local leaders was prevalent, with transportation fees often pocketed by staff.

Furthermore, aid distribution is also selective, with only 52.2% of IDPs receiving aid, predominantly those in shelters, leaving those in other housing options without support despite their needs.

The data highlights the need for more inclusive and efficient aid distribution, respectful treatment, and addressing logistical challenges. Effective humanitarian aid must address these systemic issues to enhance resilience and recovery for IDPs.

4. Lack of Experienced Volunteers:

Interviews' data revealed a volunteer shortage upon the influx of IDPs, addressed by recruiting IDPs. Moreover, training is crucial for effective humanitarian aid, yet 80% of volunteers lack proper training, causing inefficiencies. This training deficit also contributes to trust and hostility issues, as well as poor queue management.

5. Evaluation and Feedback:

According to interviews, humanitarian actors face significant challenges in evaluating and collecting feedback. Firstly, there is no formal system for gathering feedback directly from beneficiaries, which hinders the ability to tailor aid interventions effectively. Secondly, organizations tend to rely on internal feedback rather than direct input from beneficiaries, limiting their understanding of the aid's effectiveness from the recipients' perspective. Lastly, the evaluation of efficiency primarily relies on basic metrics, such as the number of people

served and healthcare services delivered, but lacks comprehensive mechanisms for incorporating beneficiary feedback. This absence of robust feedback systems ultimately limits the potential for improving humanitarian aid strategies.

In conclusion, humanitarian challenges in the Northern State include increased resource strain, health crises, and logistical issues, compounded by poor queue management and corruption. IDPs face growing needs for shelter and food due to repeated displacements. Trust issues and a lack of experienced volunteers hinder aid delivery. The absence of formal feedback mechanisms limits tailored interventions. Addressing these systemic issues with inclusive, efficient aid distribution, sustained support, and robust feedback systems is crucial for enhancing the resilience and recovery of IDPs.

- **Evolution of Needs and Priorities of IDPs in Northern State**

Survey data provides in-depth insights of IDPs needs; the analysis covers various aspects including:

Changing Needs:

Data revealed shifting priorities among IDPs. Initially, shelter was the most critical need, indicating a demand for stable housing.

Shelter's priority slightly increased from 41.57% to 48.31% over 6-12 months, highlighting its role in long-term stability. The urgency for food, water, and electricity has shown less fluctuation, highlighting the need for nuanced and adaptable responses to evolving needs.

Over time, employment opportunities became more important, with 65% prioritizing jobs, reflecting the desire for sustainable livelihoods and long-term recovery.

The dynamic nature of IDPs needs emphasizes the importance of flexible humanitarian strategies that address both immediate and long-term needs of IDPs.

Access to Services:

Data revealed a nearly equal distribution between those who have received aid (52.2%) and those who have not (47.8%). Aid recipients are predominantly located in shelters, indicating a concentration of aid in specific areas, which raises concerns about the inclusivity and effectiveness of aid distribution mechanisms for IDPs living outside formal shelters. This suggests a possible misperception by aid actors that IDPs in other accommodations are better off.

Shelter (48.9%) and food supplies (53.3%) are the most commonly received aids. However, there is a notable lack of aid for other essential needs such as chronic medication (17.78%) and women's products (5.56%). This highlights the need for a more comprehensive humanitarian aid approach addressing diverse needs beyond basic necessities.

Host community initiatives (79.4%) and aid agencies (64.7%) are the main providers of aid, while NGOs contribute less significantly (19.1%). This highlights the importance of collaboration between local community initiatives, international aid agencies, and NGOs to ensure comprehensive coverage and effectiveness in addressing the diverse needs of displaced populations. However, it also raises questions about the capacity and resources of different actors to meet the increasing aid demands.

Satisfaction levels with the aid, provided insights about aid effectiveness. The data shows mixed satisfaction levels among recipients: 39.6% report moderate satisfaction, while 29.2% and 12.5% express lesser satisfaction. This suggests that while aid provision is reaching some individuals, significant gaps and challenges remain in meeting the diverse needs and expectations of IDPs.

Addressing these challenges requires continuous monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation of aid strategies to ensure that aid is responsive, inclusive, and accountable to the needs of IDPs.

Coping Mechanisms and Future Aspirations:

A majority of IDPs (52.2%) have not accessed local resources or community networks, suggesting potential challenges in community integration and support.

Key challenges identified by respondents include issues related to shelter, lack of employment opportunities, electricity problems, and adjustment to different lifestyles. Interestingly, 42.2% of respondents indicated facing no specific challenges, which may indicate varying levels of resilience and adaptability among IDPs.

Moreover, the data highlights distinct preferences within IDPs. While a majority (64.4%) express a preference for resettling in a new location, a significant proportion (35.6%) wish to return to their original community. This divergence in preferences highlights the complex nature of displacement experiences and the importance of tailored support mechanisms.

In terms of support for future aspirations, respondents identified shelter and job opportunities as the most critical needs. However, it is noteworthy that 40% of respondents see no specific services needed, indicating a degree of uncertainty or potential adaptability to their current circumstances.

Suggestions for Improvement:

IDPs' suggestions highlight the persistent needs they face. Continuous support and permanent shelter are identified as crucial. Suggestions include respectful delivery (15.56%) emphasizing the importance of respectful aid provision.

Additionally, there are calls to regular aid provision (7.78%), reduce aid queues (5.56%) and create job opportunities (3.33%), indicating a desire for systemic change.

Although, 62.22% of respondents did not offer suggestions, potentially indicating disengagement or a lack of awareness.

Findings emphasize the multifaceted nature of the challenges and the importance of responsive aid mechanisms.

Overall, the data highlights evolving IDPs needs in Northern State and similar regions⁷, stressing immediate priorities like shelter and jobs. It highlights aid provision improvements in continuity, respect, and efficiency, with mixed satisfaction pointing to critical intervention areas.

- **Innovative Approaches for Ensuring Continuity of Aid Delivery**

In the Northern State, innovative approaches have ensured aid delivery continuity. Key strategies include expanding organizational services to meet increased demand, which allows more comprehensive responses to IDPs needs.

Integrating training programs for healthcare and small enterprises has addressed both immediate and long-term needs, equipping IDPs with essential skills to cope with current challenges and fostering future self-reliance and economic stability.

Despite the lack of formal feedback mechanisms, some organizations use basic metrics and internal feedback to monitor and adjust aid delivery in real-time. This foundational step paves the way for more sophisticated evaluation methods.

Additionally, the flexibility and adaptability of humanitarian organizations have been crucial, enabling rapid strategic changes in response to evolving conditions.

These strategies collectively enhanced the resilience and effectiveness of humanitarian aid, ensuring it remains responsive and continuous in a dynamic conflict environment.

⁷ Nile River, Red Sea, and eastern states.

- **Recommendations for Humanitarian Actors:**

1. **Invest in Local Capacity Building:** Localization of aid delivery should be pursued with caution, ensuring that local actors receive adequate support and resources to effectively respond to humanitarian needs. This includes providing training and technical assistance to local organizations, empowering them to play a significant role in aid provision.
2. **Improve Feedback Mechanisms:** prioritize collecting, analyzing, and acting upon beneficiary feedback to enhance the relevance and effectiveness of aid programs.
3. **Adaptation and Innovation:** Embrace flexibility and adaptability in aid delivery strategies to respond effectively to evolving conflict dynamics and community needs. Investing in innovative approaches as technology-driven solutions and community-led initiatives can help overcome operational challenges and ensure aid continuity.
4. **Transparency and Accountability:** Implement strict measures to combat corruption and ensure equitable distribution of aid.
5. **Long-term Support and Economic Stability:** Shift focus from immediate relief to long-term support, including healthcare and economic opportunities, develop programs to support small enterprises and economic stability for IDPs.

Conclusion:

The study highlights the need for comprehensive support amid complex challenges. Despite security threats, bureaucratic hurdles, and resource scarcity, humanitarian actors strive to meet evolving needs.

Focusing on the Northern State, the study highlights the importance of tailored strategies, such as expanding services, integrating training programs, and enhancing flexibility.

Recommendations include investing in local capacity building, improving feedback mechanisms, fostering adaptation and innovation, ensuring transparency and accountability, and prioritizing long-term support. Implementing these strategies can enhance aid resilience and effectiveness, fostering recovery and stability in conflict-affected areas.

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